

GATEWAYS TO ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: DEVELOPING A TAXONOMY FOR AI SERVICE PLATFORMS

Interview Questionnaire

Chapter 1: Introduction of interview partners and research project

- 1.1. What is your personal, educational, and professional background?
- 1.2. What is your current professional activity?
- 1.3. What are your touchpoints to AI platforms there?

Chapter 2: General statements on AI platforms

- 2.1. What is your understanding of artificial intelligence platforms?
- 2.2. Do you use AI platforms? If yes, which ones?
- 2.3. What experiences have you had with AI platforms?

Chapter 3: Taxonomy presentation and evaluation

- 3.1. Do you understand all the dimensions and characteristics?
- 3.2. Do you have any suggestions for improving the terminology?
- 3.3. Do you have any suggestions for changes regarding the dimensions and characteristics?
- 3.4. How do you assess the completeness of the taxonomy?
- 3.5. Which further dimensions and/or characteristics would you like to have included?
- 3.6. Do you consider one or more dimensions and/or characteristics as not contributive to the taxonomy's value?

Situational: Taxonomy deployment in practice

- 4.1. *Do you use taxonomies for decision support when selecting software products?*
- 4.2. *Are you interested in using the taxonomy and research results in your company as decision support for the selection of AI platforms?*